

QUICK PHOTO GUIDE TO THE SOUTH AFRICAN THOMISUS SPECIES

Ansie Dippenaar Schoeman
Adjunct professor University of Venda

For more information and credits for photographs see
Dippenaar-Schoeman A.S., Haddad C.R., Foord S.H., & Lotz L.N. (2020) *The Thomisidae of South Africa*. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: The Thomisidae of South Africa (S-T) Part 3, Version 1: 1-79.
Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7513278>

1. *Thomisus australis* Comellini, 1957

2. *Thomisus blandus* Karsch, 1880

3. *Thomisus citrinellus* Simon, 1875

4. *Thomisus congoensis* Comellini, 1957 only male

5. *Thomisus dalmasi* Lessert, 1919

6. *Thomisus daradioides* Simon, 1890

7. *Thomisus ghesquierei* Lessert, 1943 only female

8. *Thomisus granulatus* Karsch, 1880

9. *Thomisus kalaharinus* Lawrence, 1936

10. *Thomisus machadoi* Comellini, 1959 only male

11. *Thomisus natalensis* Lawrence, 1942 only female

12. *Thomisus schultzei* Simon, 1910 only female

13. *Thomisus scrupeus* (Simon, 1886)

14. *Thomisus spiculosus* Pocock, 1901

15. *Thomisus stenningi* Pocock, 1900

16. *Thomisus zuluanus* Lawrence, 1942 only female

